

MODELING THE KINETICS OF DRYING BEET ROOTS

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Introduction. Drying involves complex thermal processes in which mass and heat are transferred simultaneously, interrelatedly and unstably both inside and on the surface of the sample. Accordingly, it is necessary to have a complete understanding of the control parameters in this process. In the literature, the drying process is described using three mathematical models: theoretical, semi-theoretical and empirical [1, 2]. Understanding the basic phenomena and mechanisms of the drying process helps to develop various theoretical models. Both theoretical models and computer simulations are used as a means to predict the drying curves of various products.

Theoretical calculations and process modeling are able to explain the phenomena occurring during the drying process. Empirical models can be built on the basis of a direct correlation of humidity with drying time without taking into account the principles of this process. Accordingly, empirically developed models can predict drying curves for real conditions. However, their parameters have no physical meaning and are not able to accurately explain the important phenomena of the process. As a compromise between theory and convenient application, semi-theoretical models are derived from a simplified second law of Fick's diffusion or are obtained by modifying any simplified widely used model [3].

The aim of this work was to study the drying process of crushed beetroot using hot air and infrared drying methods and find the best drying model to explain the drying of crushed plant materials with hot air and infrared radiation.

Materials and methods. Fresh beets were collected and crushed before each series of experiments. Beets were selected based on visual assessment of their uniformity, color and size.

The initial moisture content was $82.2 \pm 0.2\%$. Before each experiment, large, uncrushed beets were removed from the mass.

A laboratory setup consisting of a drying chamber, an air flow control unit, temperature control unit, and radiation source (infrared lamp and electric heater) was developed for the research. The drying chamber was made of sheet metal, the outer surface of which was completely insulated to prevent heat loss to the environment by an additional casing. A heater power control unit was used to regulate the air temperature. The temperature inside the drying chamber was constantly monitored by a thermocouple, which was built into the control element. A digital anemometer was used to measure the air velocity. A 250 W infrared lamp was installed on the upper side of the drying chamber. The height of the lamp was adjusted by a tripod. The intensity of infrared radiation was adjusted by an autotransformer.

For the hot air drying experiments, different air flow rates at three levels of 0.5, 1 and 1.5 m/s and three temperatures at three levels of 30, 45 and 60°C were selected. In addition, different irradiance levels (1500, 3000 and 4500 W/m²), lamp-to-sample distances (10, 30 and 50 cm) and air flow rates (0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 m/s) were used for infrared drying. The temperature and air flow rates were selected based on a literature review of industrial air drying applications, in particular, thin-layer drying of medicinal plants. As practice shows, low temperatures (i.e. 30–50°C) should be used for drying plants in order to obtain an optimal product quality without losing protein and protein. Before each experiment, the dryer was left idle for approximately 30 minutes to ensure a steady state based on the predetermined experimental drying conditions. For each treatment, 200 ± 1 g of plant material was uniformly spread in a thin layer on an aluminum weighing bottle.

Drying was stopped once the sample moisture content reached the target 10-13%. All drying procedures were performed in triplicate. Drying curves were then plotted using the average moisture content at each time point.

The mass fraction of moisture in percent in the test sample was calculated using the formula:

$$X = \frac{m_2 - m_3}{m_2 - m_1} \cdot 100, \quad (1)$$

where X is the mass fraction of moisture, %; m_1 is the mass of the weighing bottle without the test sample, g; m_2 is the mass of the weighing bottle with the test sample before drying, g; m_3 is the mass of the weighing bottle with the test sample after drying, g.

The energy expended in evaporation of moisture was calculated. The energy expended in evaporation was calculated using the Arrhenius equation [1, 2]:

$$D_{Ar} = D_o \exp\left(-\frac{E_3}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where D_o is the pre-exponential coefficient of the Arrhenius equation, E_3 is the energy of evaporation (kJ/mol), R is the ideal gas constant (8.314 J/kmol), T is the drying temperature.

Results and discussion. The time required for drying the crushed plant material is described in detail in our previous works [4, 5]. The graphs of the experimental data on hot air drying of crushed plant material at different temperatures (30, 40 and 50°C) and air flow rates (0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 m/s) were analyzed in terms of the decrease in the moisture content as a function of the drying time. This is due to the fact that the moisture content curves explain the drying behavior of the products better than the final moisture content curves, since the initial moisture content for all experiments was compared to 82.2%.

The results of the study showed that temperature had the most significant effect on the drying kinetics of the samples. Air flow rate had the second most significant effect.

The effect of infrared radiation level on the moisture content of the samples was significant, as expected. Both at constant air flow rate and at varying distance between the emitter and the sample, the moisture content decreased faster with increasing infrared radiation level. The results of infrared drying showed that, in contrast to hot air drying, the moisture content decreased faster with decreasing air flow rate at the same infrared radiation intensity and emitter-sample distance. Increasing the air flow rate increased the cooling effect, which decreased the temperature of the product.

At the same infrared radiation intensity and air flow rate, the decrease in moisture release accelerates when the infrared emitter is placed closer to the sample. As the distance between the sample and the emitter increases, the thermal radiation hits the surface of the sample but does not effectively penetrate inside. Therefore, the absorbed moisture energy inside the leaves of the sample decreases sharply. Accordingly, the degree of moisture removal decreased due to the increase in the distance between the infrared emitter and the sample.

Fig. 1 shows the moisture diffusion values at different temperatures and air flow rates. It is expected that the moisture diffusion values increase with increasing drying temperature. This was due to the increase in the vapor pressure of the samples, which accelerated the moisture exchange at higher

temperatures. When drying plants at a higher temperature, the heating energy increases, which leads to an increase in the activity of water molecules. As a result, higher moisture diffusion values can be obtained.

Using higher air flow rates at all drying temperatures results in higher moisture diffusion values. This may be due to the lower vapor pressure resulting from the higher air flow rate, which in turn reduces the evaporative resistance.

Fig. 1. Effect of air velocity and temperature on the effective diffusion coefficient during hot air drying of crushed beets

The lowest moisture diffusion value was observed at 0.5 m/s air flow velocity at 30°C, while its highest value was recorded using 50°C drying air at 1.5 m/s. These results indicated that higher air temperature and air velocity were preferable for drying the ground plant material when using hot air drying under the given experimental conditions. The effect of air temperature on the moisture diffusion of the ground plant material was greater than that of air flow velocity.

$$D_{Ar} = 10^{-12} \cdot (0,11T + 5,9V + 0,01T^2 - 1,39V^2 + 0,59),$$

$$R^2 = 0,98 \quad (3)$$

The calculated moisture evaporation values for the ground plant material during infrared drying are shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen from the figure that the moisture diffusion increases when the infrared intensity increases at a constant air flow rate and a constant distance between the emitter and the

sample. This can be caused by the increased levels of infrared intensity, which quickly increases the temperature of the sample. As a result, the vapor pressure also increased, leading to faster drying.

Fig. 2. Change in the effective diffusion coefficient depending on the intensity of infrared radiation, air velocity and distance to the sample

Studies on shredded cabbage also showed similar effects of infrared radiation on moisture diffusion. Increasing the air flow velocity at a constant infrared intensity and distance between the emitter and the sample reduces moisture diffusion. This is because the faster air flow cools the surface of the sample, while the internal temperature of the sample remains relatively higher than the surface and ambient air temperatures. This results in a negative temperature gradient. For drying with an IR heat source, the lowest moisture diffusion value was at an air flow velocity of 1.5 m/s, a radiant intensity of 1500 W/m² and a distance between the emitter and the sample of 20 cm, while the highest moisture diffusion value was recorded at an air velocity of 0.5 m/s.

The moisture diffusion values from this study were in the range of 10.1 to 10.8 m²/s for drying plant materials. Accordingly, the highest moisture diffusion values were related to the infrared drying experiments. This is mainly due to the fact that the drying time in the infrared dryer is much shorter than that of the hot air drying system. Therefore, the infrared drying method was found to be more effective in drying the shredded plant material than the hot air drying.

Conclusions. The drying kinetics of ground plant materials under two drying methods, hot air and infrared drying, were analyzed and modeled. In

both drying methods, moisture removal was observed during the decreasing velocity period rather than during the constant velocity period. The drying efficiency of infrared drying was higher than that of hot air drying due to its higher drying velocity. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the mass transfer mechanism of ground plant materials during the drying process, the effective moisture diffusion was also determined. It was found that the moisture diffusion values ranged from $1.096 \cdot 10^{-11}$ to $2.486 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and from $3.312 \cdot 10^{-11}$ to $5.928 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for hot air drying and infrared drying, respectively. In hot air drying, the moisture diffusion value was greater at higher temperatures and higher air flow rates.

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